

Petrological Studies of Metamorphic Rocks and Economic Aspects in Kyauktaga and Its Environs, Kyaikhto Township, Mon State

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Abstract

The studied area located in the western part of Kyaikhtiyo area, Kyaikhto Township, Mon State. The metamorphic and igneous rocks are found in the study area. Metamorphic rocks consist of slate, phyllite and quartzite, actinolite-chlorite phyllite, biotite-quartz schist, quartzite, hornfels and skarn. Most metamorphic rocks are foliated, showing slaty, phyllitic, and schistose textures. Some are non-foliated, which show granoblastics and hornfelsic textures. The essential minerals are quartz, biotite, muscovite, sericite, actinolite, chlorite, cordierite, hornblende, tremolite, plagioclase and orthoclase. According to the mineralogical and textural features, the metamorphic rocks of the study area had undergone regional and contact metamorphism. The metamorphic facies are greenschist facies of regional metamorphism and hornblende hornfels facies of contact metamorphism. P-T condition is estimated about 300°C to 500°C and 2 kb to 3.8 kb in regional metamorphism, and 500°C to 650°C and 1 kb to 2 kb in contact metamorphism. Gold is distinct mineral deposit in the study area.

Introduction

Location

The studied area located in the western part of Kyaikhtiyo area, Kyaikhto Township, Mon State. It lies between Latitude 17° 25' to 17° 30'N and Longitude 96° 59' to 97° 4'E and is situated between horizontal grids no.13 to 21 and vertical grids no.50 to 59 in one inch topographic map sheet no. 94 C/15 and 94 G/ 3 of Myanmar Survey Department. Location map of the area is shown in (Figure 1).

Objectives

1. To study and interpret the petrography, types of metamorphism and petrogenesis of each rock unit.
2. To express the possible economic aspects of the study area.

Methods of study

1. Rock samples were acquired at all points where they have change in characters.
2. For detailed microscopic study, about 20 thin sections were made from the representative samples of each rock unit.

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Figure 1. Location map of the study area.

Rock Sequence

Metamorphic rocks of the study area are Mergui Group (Early Carboniferous). These rocks are subdivided into five units. The rock sequence of the study area is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Rock sequence of the study area

Metamorphic Rocks

Petrography

General Statement

Metamorphic rock units consist of slate, phyllite and quartzite, actinolite-chlorite phyllite, biotite-quartz schist, quartzite, hornfels and skarn. The classification of these rock units is based on their textural and structural criteria, field evidences and microscopic study of mineral assemblages.

Slate, phyllite and quartzite

Field and megascopic studies

This unit is well distributed through out the western part of the study area, especially in Inkabo chaung, slopes of Kyaukgyi taung, Gu Ku gold mine (Loc.G524145) and Peinnegone village. Slate is very fine-grained and foliated. It is soft, friable and steeply dipping to the west (Figure 2). Phyllite shows sheen on the surface of foliation plane. It is soft, friable, distorted, steeply dipping and microfolding are also observed (Figure 3). The colour of phyllite is brownish grey on weathered surface and grey on fresh surface.

Quartzite shows massive and fairly jointed nature (Figure 4). The colour is dark grey on weathered surface and light grey on fresh surface. It is hard, compact and fine-grained.

Microscopic studies

Slate is fine-grained, foliated and slaty texture. The included minerals are quartz, biotite, chlorite and iron ore. In slate, quartz grains are aggregated as lens-shaped form and show lengthen and flaky nature along the foliation plane (Figure 5). Biotite is subhedral flaky mineral and shows brown colour. In some places, biotite is altered to chlorite along the margin and twin plane. Phyllite is fine-grained and foliated texture (Figure 6). It is composed of quartz, muscovite, biotite and chlorite. In phyllite, quartz grains are anhedral granular form and show undulatory extinction.

Quartzite is fine-grained and granoblastic texture. The constituent minerals are quartz, sericite, mica and iron ore (Figure 7).

The characteristic mineral assemblages of the rock units are:

1. Quartz + biotite + chlorite + iron ore (slate)
2. Quartz + muscovite + biotite + chlorite (phyllite)
3. Quartz + sericite (quartzite)

Figure. 2. Steeply dipping foliated nature of slate in western part of Meyongyi chaung (Loc.G525 136).

Figure. 3. Highly weathered and steeply dipping of phyllite at Gu Ku gold mine area (Loc.G523 144).

Figure. 4. Massive and fairly jointed nature of quartzite in the eastern part of Peinnegone village (Loc.G505 189).

Figure. 5. Lens-shaped quartz in slate.

Figure. 6. Phyllitic texture in phyllite.

Figure. 7. Sericite minerals in quartzite.

Actinolite-chlorite phyllite

Field and megascopic studies

Actinolite-chlorite phyllite is commonly occurred in the western part of this area. It is fine-grained, soft, friable and highly jointed (Figure 8). The colour is purplish red on weathered surface and greenish grey on fresh surface.

Microscopic studies

It is fine-grained and phyllitic texture. It is composed of quartz, biotite, chlorite, actinolite, and opaque minerals. Actinolite is anhedral and fibrous form (Figure 9). Quartz is anhedral granular aggregate form and shows wavy extinction. Occasionally, suture contact is observed.

Biotite is subhedral form and yellowish brown colour. Pale green chlorite was altered from biotite. Iron ore is found as opaque mineral.

The characteristic mineral assemblages of this rock unit are:

1. Actinolite + chlorite + quartz + biotite + iron ore
2. Chlorite + quartz + biotite

Figure 8. Outcrop nature of actinolite-chlorite phyllite at Inkabo chaung (Loc.G520 158).

Figure 9. Actinolite minerals in actinolite-chlorite phyllite.

Biotite-quartz schist

Field and megascopic studies

This rock unit is mainly observed in the southeastern part of Sindwin village and stream sections, especially at Loc.G518 204 (Figure 10). It is medium-grained, foliated and schistose texture. The colour is grey on fresh surface and reddish brown on weathered surface. It is highly weathered and highly jointed nature.

Microscopic studies

It is composed of quartz, biotite, chlorite and iron ore. Quartz grains are anhedral crystals and show wavy extinction due to strain effect. Biotite exhibits subhedral, long prismatic forms and foliated nature (Figure 11). In some places, biotite altered to chlorite and sericite. Iron ore is present as accessory mineral.

The characteristic mineral assemblages of the rock unit are:

1. Quartz + biotite + chlorite + iron ore
2. Quartz + biotite + sericite + iron ore

Figure. 10. Outcrop nature of biotite-quartz schist at Sindwin chaung (Loc.G518 204).

Figure. 11. Foliated nature of biotite in biotite-quartz schist.

Quartzite

Field and megascopic studies

It is mainly exposed along the stream sections and mountain peak of the study area (Loc.G535193). It is hard, compact, massive and fairly jointed nature (Figure 12). The fresh colour is light grey and weathered colour is dark grey.

Microscopic studies

It is medium-grained and granular texture. It is mainly composed of quartz and iron ore as accessory mineral. Most quartz grains show wavy extinction and suture contact (Figure 13). The characteristic mineral assemblage of this rock unit is:

1. Quartz + iron ore

Figure. 12. Massive and fairly jointed nature of quartzite at Kadaingdut chaung (Loc.G535193).

Figure. 13. Wavy extinction and suture contact of quartz in quartzite.

Hornfels and skarn

Field and megascopic studies

Hornfels are commonly exposed in the western part of Saungnaing village, sides of Meyongyi-Kadaingdut road, and vicinity of Mobaw chaung (Loc.G527 201) (Figure 14). It is fairly exposed and highly weathered. Weathered colour is reddish brown and dark grey on fresh surface.

Skarn is mainly exposed along the stream sections of Sindwin chaung (Loc.G515 202). It is massive nature and has solution holes on the surface (Figure 18). Dark grey colour on weathered surface and fresh surface is bluish grey in colour.

Microscopic studies

Hornfels is fine to medium-grained, non-foliated and hornfelsic texture. It consists of hornblende, plagioclase, cordierite, k-feldspar, biotite, quartz and iron ore minerals.

Hornblende is subhedral form (Figure 15). It exhibits yellowish green colour under PPL and second order yellowish brown colour between X.N. In basal section, two sets of cleavage (56° & 124°) are observed.

Plagioclase shows anhedral prismatic form as lath-shape. In some section, it is altered to sericite. K-feldspar is anhedral form and shows both simple twinned and untwinned nature. Biotite is occurred as minor amounts. Aggregates of biotite are found as opaque minerals in some sections. Spotted nature is also occurred (Figure 16). Spots are formed by the presence of cordierite or andalusite minerals. Cordierite occurs as six-sided crystal (Figure 17). Iron ore is present as accessory mineral.

Skarn shows medium to coarse-grained and includes diopside, tremolite, forsterite, calcite and iron ore minerals.

Tremolite is observed as long prismatic, acicular and fibrous forms (Figure 19). It is colourless under PPL and second order greenish brown between X.N. Calcite occur as anhedral rhomb-shaped form (Figure 20). Iron ore is present as accessory mineral. The characteristic mineral assemblages of these rock units are:

1. Hornblende + quartz + k-feldspar + iron ore (Hornfels)
2. Hornblende + cordierite + plagioclase + k-feldspar + biotite (Hornfels)
3. Quartz + sericite + iron ore (Hornfels)
4. Diopside + tremolite + forsterite + calcite + iron ore (Skarn)

Figure. 14. Exposure nature of hornfels at Mobaw chaung (Loc. G527 201).

Figure. 15. Subhedral form of hornblende mineral in hornfels.

Figure. 16. Spotted nature of hornfels.

Figure. 17. Cordierite crystal in hornfels.

Figure. 18. Solution holes in skarn at Sindwin chaung (Loc.G515 202).

Figure. 19. Accicular and fibrous form of tremolite in skarn.

Figure. 20. Calcite in skarn.

Petrogenesis

Types of Metamorphism and Metamorphic Facies

According to the occurrences of mineral assemblages, two main types of metamorphism and metamorphic facies are observed in the study area – greenschist facies of regional metamorphism and hornblende-hornfels facies of contact metamorphism.

Greenschist Facies

The greenschist facies is noted by the presence of actinolite, biotite, chlorite, muscovite, quartz, sericite and iron ore minerals. AKF diagram for greenschist facies of regional metamorphism is shown in (Figure 21). The mineral assemblages are:

Slate, phyllite and quartzite unit

1. Quartz + biotite + chlorite + iron ore
2. Quartz + biotite + muscovite + chlorite

3. Quartz + sericite
Actinolite-chlorite phyllite
4. Actinolite + chlorite + quartz + biotite + iron ore
Biotite-quartz schist
5. Quartz + biotite + chlorite + iron ore
Quartzite
6. Quartz + iron ore

Hornblende-hornfels Facies

The hornblende-hornfels facies is recognized by the presence of hornblende, quartz, biotite, plagioclase, k-feldspar, cordierite, tremolite, calcite and sericite. AKF and ACF diagrams for hornblende-hornfels facies of contact metamorphism are shown in (Figure 22, 23). The mineral assemblages are:

Hornfels unit

1. Hornblende + quartz + k-feldspar + iron ore
2. Hornblende + cordierite + plagioclase + k-feldspar + biotite
3. Quartz + sericite + iron ore

Skarn unit

4. Diopside + tremolite + forsterite + calcite + iron ore

Figure. 21. AKF diagram for greenschist facies of regional metamorphism (Winter, 2010)

Figure. 22. AKF diagram for hornblende-hornfels facies of contact metamorphism (Winter, 2010).

Figure. 23. ACF diagram for hornblende-hornfels facies of contact metamorphism (Winter, 2010).

Estimation of P-T condition

The metamorphic facies of the study area and their generally accepted pressure and temperature limits are shown in (Figure 24).

In regional metamorphism, P-T condition may be considered based on the following points;

1. The stability of greenschist minerals are about 300°C to 500°C and 2 to 3.8 kb (Winter, 2010).

In contact metamorphism, P-T condition may be regarded according to the following factors:

1. Occurrence of cordierite in contact metamorphic rocks shows that estimated temperature was 500°C to 650°C and pressure was 1 to 2 kb.
2. Tremolite and calcite which are found in skarn suggest that estimated temperature was 550°C to 650°C and pressure was 1 to 2 kb.

Thus, P-T condition of contact metamorphism is about 500°C to 650°C and 1 to 2 kb.

Figure. 24. Pressure-temperature diagram showing the generally accepted limits of two facies of the study area (Winter, 2010).

Economic Aspects

Gold

Economically, many gold mines are especially found in the study area. Gold bearing quartz veins are associated with quartzite units in the study area. It is excavated by using various methods in both primary and secondary deposits (Figures 25, 26, 27). In primary deposits, it is excavated by using underground method. But, in secondary deposit, local people extract gold from placer deposits by using hydrolic pumping method, panning method and etc. The gold is formed by hypogene process and the mineralization zone lies within the NW-SE strike slip fault system (Zaw Naing Oo, 1998).

Figure. 25. Gold excavation from placer deposits at Inkabo chaung (Loc.G520 158).

Figure. 26. Gold mineral resulted from placer deposit at Sindwin village (Loc. 505 208).

Figure. 27. Gold mineralization in quartz vein at Gu Ku gold mine area (Loc.G524 145).

Conclusion

The studied area situated in the western part of Kyaikhtiyo area, Kyaikhto Township, Mon State. The metamorphic rocks are subdivided into slate, phyllite and quartzite, Actinolite-chlorite phyllite, biotite-quartz schist, quartzite, hornfels and skarn. These rocks include in Mergui Group which was Early Carboniferous age. According to mineralogical and textural features, the rocks of the study area had undergone greenschist facies of regional metamorphism and hornblende-hornfels facies of contact metamorphism. According to mineral assemblages, the estimated P-T condition of the study area is 300°C to 500°C and 2 kb to 3.8 kb for regional metamorphism and 500°C to 650°C and 1 kb to 2 kb for contact metamorphism. Economically, primary and placer gold deposits are found in the study area. Gold bearing quartz veins are associated with quartzite units. The gold is formed by hypogene process and the mineralization zone lies within the NW-SE strike-slip fault system.

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